

BIM-BASED DEVELOPMENT OF BILL OF MATERIALS WITH CASE STUDY

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Abstract

This thesis emphasizes the research and methodology impacting BIM (Building Information Modelling), beginning with the problems arising after the project is modeled to its 3rd, 4th, and 5th dimensions. Most BIM projects stop after the model is done and not use it for Schedules and Bill of Quantities (4D and 5D).

The research started with a survey, taken by companies all around the world. The companies are selected based on their experience in the 4th and 5th dimension in BIM and Quantity Surveying. As well as hearing their comments regarding the advantages and disadvantages of the process, such as time, price, quality, and accuracy. There are a lot of concerns that are common between firms such as the level of security in the project and the accurate readings generated from the project.

First of all, The traditional style of BOQ generation (Manual) is used by many firms, The case study got implemented and the result is used in the next step of the research. Later on, a semi-traditional style was done (using CostX). PDF plans from the models were extracted and then imported to the software, the readings were recorded in the Quantity Takeoff (QTO) and then organized in the New Rules of Measurement Bill of Quantity Template. Last but not least, a prototype plug-in was used to generate the readings in which later generated organized in the Bill of Quantity template. The higher the Level of Detail (LOD) of the project, the more accurate the reading will be. To conclude, the model will be tested in three BOQ methods (Traditional, Semi Intervention, Plug-in).

The final reading (traditional, Semi-traditional, Plug-in) is given to experts and the outcome was graded based on several matters such as time, accuracy, and template, and the data will be analyzed to draw conclusions and formulate questions for future research. A feedback review of the QTO and BOQ is done with NRM II adaption. The research is tested on all continents.

Therefore, finding a smart and practical solution that will revolutionize the thinking methodology of the quantity surveyor profession. A test trial of a real model is done and the outcome is reviewed by experts in that field, its a refurbishment project of a music academy located in Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Dissertation:

https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-NabihMousharbash-Dissertation_compressed.pdf

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/f0tgGo0VaTs>

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